

Noetherian Rings And Modules

Jeremiah Adedoyin

November 30, 2023

Abstract

Although Noetherianity is often too strong an assumption, the ring of integers, Dedekind domains, and a host of other rings from number theory and ideal theory that are Noetherian are all evidence that they simply show up "in nature" a lot. Algebraic geometers care a great deal about polynomial rings $\mathbb{F}[x_1, \dots, x_n]$ over fields, which are Noetherian. In a nice case like $\mathbb{F} = \mathbb{C}$, the resulting connection between the Noetherianness of the ring and the Noetherianness of topologies on algebraic varieties allows decompositions of the varieties. The primary decomposition, as will be defined in this presentation, is a direct generalization of prime factorization of integers and polynomials. The most important result of Noetherianity is seen in Theorem 3.2. In this presentation, I intend to give a proper definition of the Noetherian rings and modules. Also, I shall prove the Krull Intersection Theorem, Nakayama's Lemma, and the Hilbert Basis Theorem, with some applications.

1 Introduction

Definition 1.1. A module A is said to be **Noetherian** if it satisfy the **ascending chain condition (ACC) on submodules** i.e., if for every chain $A_1 \subset A_2 \subset A_3 \subset \dots$ of submodules of A , there is an integer n such that $A_i = A_n$ for all $i \geq n$.

Definition 1.2. A ring R is left (resp. right) **Noetherian** if R satisfies the ascending chain condition on left (resp. right) ideals. R is said to be **Noetherian** if R is both left and right Noetherian.

Examples. The Z -module (abelian group) Z satisfies the ascending chain condition on submodules. Also, Z is also a Noetherian ring. In particular, every finitely generated modules satisfies the A.C.C. condition on its submodules. A division ring D is Noetherian since the only ideals of D are D and 0 . Every P.I.D. is Noetherian. In particular, $Z, Z_n, F[x]$ where F is a field are Noetherian.

Definition 1.3. Let I be an ideal in a commutative ring R . The **radical** of I , denoted $RadI$, is the ideal $\bigcap P$, where the intersection is taken over all prime ideals P that contain I . If the set of prime ideals containing I is empty, then $RadI$ is defined to be R .

Definition 1.4. An ideal $Q (\neq R)$ in a commutative ring R is **primary** if for any $a, b \in R : ab \in Q$ and $a \notin Q \implies b^n \in Q$ for some $n > 0$.

Definition 1.5. An ideal I in a commutative ring R has a **primary decomposition** if $I = Q_1 \cap Q_2 \cap Q_3 \cap \dots \cap Q_n$ with each Q_i primary. If no Q_i contains $Q_1 \cap Q_2 \cap \dots \cap Q_{i-1} \cap Q_{i+1} \cap \dots \cap Q_n$ and the radicals of the Q_i are all distinct, then the primary decomposition is said to be **reduced**.

Definition 1.6. Let R be a commutative ring with identity and B be an R -module. A submodule $A (\neq B)$ is **primary** provided that if $r \in R, b \notin A$ and $rb \in A \implies r^n B \subset A$ for some positive integer n and $b \in B$.

Definition 1.7. A primary submodule A of an R -module B (R is commutative with identity) is said to **belong to a prime ideal \mathbf{P}** or to be a **\mathbf{P} -primary submodule** of B if $P = RadQ_A = \{r \in R \mid r^n B \subset A \text{ for some } n > 0\}$ where $Q_A = \{r \in R \mid rB \subset A\}$.

Definition 1.8. Let R be a commutative ring with identity and B be an R -module. A submodule C of B has a **primary decomposition** if $C = A_1 \cap A_2 \cap A_3 \cap \dots \cap A_n$ with each A_i a P_i -primary submodule of B for some ideal P_i of R . If no A_i contains $A_1 \cap A_2 \cap \dots \cap A_{i-1} \cap A_{i+1} \cap \dots \cap A_n$ and if the ideals P_i are all distinct, then the primary decomposition is said to be **reduced**.

2 Results on Noetherian Rings and Modules

2.1 Krull Intersection Theorem

Theorem 2.1.1. Let R be a commutative ring with identity and B be an R -module satisfying the ascending chain condition on submodules. Then every submodule $A (\neq B)$ has a reduced primary decomposition. In particular, every submodule $A (\neq B)$ of a finitely generated module B over a commutative Noetherian ring R and every ideal $I (\neq R)$ of R has a reduced primary decomposition.

Proof. Omitted.

Lemma 2.1.2. Let P be a prime ideal in a commutative ring R with identity. If C is a P -primary submodule of the Noetherian R -module A , then there exists a positive integer m such that $P^m A \subset C$.

Proof. Omitted

Theorem 2.1.3. (Krull Intersection Theorem). Let R be a commutative ring with identity, I an ideal of R , and A a Noetherian R -module. If $B = \bigcap_{n=1}^{\infty} I^n A$, then $IB = B$.

Proof. If $IB = A$, then $A = IB \subset B$, whence $B = A = IB$. If $IB \neq A$, then by Theorem 2.1.1, IB has a primary decomposition:

$$IB = A_1 \cap A_2 \cap A_3 \cap \dots \cap A_s$$

where each A_i is a P_i -primary submodule of A for some prime ideal P_i of R . Since $IB \subset B$ in any case, we only need to show that $B \subset A_i$ for every i in order to conclude that $B \subset IB$ and hence that $B = IB$.

Let $i (1 < i < s)$ be fixed. Suppose first that $I \subset P_i$. By Lemma 2.1.2, there is an integer m such that $P_i^m A \subset A_i$, hence $B = \bigcap_n I^n A \subset I^m A \subset P_i^m A \subset A_i$.

Now suppose $I \not\subset P_i$. Then there exists $r \in I - P_i$. If $B \not\subset A_i$, then there exists $b \in B - A_i$. Since $rb \in IB \subset A_i$, $b \notin A_i$ and A_i is primary, $r^n A \subset A_i$ for some $n > 0$. Consequently, $r \in P_i$ since A_i is a P_i -primary submodule. This contradicts the choice of $r \in I - P_i$. Therefore, $B \subset A_i$. The proof is complete.

2.2 Nakayama's Lemma

If J is an ideal in a commutative ring R with identity, then the following conditions are equivalent.

- (i) J is contained in every maximal ideal of R ;
- (ii) $1_R - j$ is a unit for every $j \in J$;
- (iii) If A is a finitely generated R -module such that $JA = A$, then $A = 0$;
- (iv) If B is a submodule of a finitely generated R -module A such that $A = JA + B$, then $A = B$.

proof. (i) \implies (ii) if $j \in J$ and $1_R - j$ is not a unit, then the ideal $(1_R - j)$ is not R itself and therefore is contained in a maximal ideal $M \neq R$ (Since in a nonzero ring R with identity, every ideal in R is contained in a maximal ideal). But $1_R - j \in M$ and $j \in J \subset M$ imply that $1_R \in M$, which is a contradiction. Therefore, $1_R - j$ is a unit.

(ii) \implies (iii) Since A is finitely generated, there must be a minimal generating set $X = \{a_1, \dots, a_n\}$ of A (that is, no proper subset of X generates A). If $A \neq 0$, then $a_1 \neq 0$ by minimality. Since $JA = A$, $a_1 = j_1 a_1 + j_2 a_2 + \dots + j_n a_n$ ($j_i \in J$), whence $1_R a_1 = a_1$ so that $(1_R - j_1)a_1 = 0$ if $n = 1$ and if $n > 1$ then we have

$$(1_R - j_1)a_1 = j_2 a_2 + \dots + j_n a_n$$

Since $1_R - j_1$ is a unit in R , $a_1 = (1_R - j_1)^{-1}(j_2 a_2 + \dots + j_n a_n)$. Thus if $n = 1$, then $a_1 = 0$ which is a contradiction. If $n > 1$, then a_1 is a linear combination of a_2, \dots, a_n . Consequently, $\{a_2, \dots, a_n\}$ generates

A , which contradicts the choice of X .

(iii) \implies (iv) Verify that the quotient module A/B is such that $J(A/B) = A/B$, whence $A/B = 0$ and $A = B$ by (iii).

(iv) \implies (i) If M is any maximal ideal, then the ideal $JR + M$ contains M . But $JR + M \neq R$ (otherwise $R = M$ by (iv)). Consequently, $JR + M = M$ by maximality. Therefore, $J = JR \subset M$. The proof is complete.

2.3 Hilbert Basis Theorem

Theorem 2.3.1. A module A satisfies the ascending chain condition on submodules if and only if every submodule of A is finitely generated. In particular, a commutative ring R is Noetherian if and only if every ideal of R is finitely generated.

Proof. Omitted.

Theorem 2.3.2. (Hilbert Basis Theorem). If R is a commutative Noetherian ring with identity, then so is $R[x_1, \dots, x_n]$.

Proof. Clearly, it suffices to show that $R[x]$ is Noetherian. By Theorem 2.3.1, we only need to show that every ideal J in $R[x]$ is finitely generated. For each $n > 0$, let I_n be the set of all $r \in R$ such that $r = 0$ or r is the leading coefficient of a polynomial $f \in J$ of degree n . Verify that each I_n is an ideal of R . If r is a nonzero element of I_n and $f \in J$ is a polynomial of degree n with leading coefficient r , then r is also the leading coefficient of xf , which is a polynomial in J of degree $n + 1$. Hence $I_0 \subset I_1 \subset I_2 \subset \dots$. Since R is Noetherian, there exists an integer t such that $I_n = I_t$ for all $n \geq t$; furthermore, by Theorem 2.3.1, each $I_n (n \geq 0)$ is finitely generated say $I_n = (r_{n1}, r_{n2}, \dots, r_{ni_n})$. For each r_{nj} with $0 \leq n \leq t$ and $1 \leq j \leq i_n$, let $f_{nj} \in J$ be a polynomial of degree n with leading coefficient r_{nj} . Observe that $f_{0j} = r_{0j} \in R \subset R[x]$. We shall show that the ideal J of $R[x]$ is generated by the finite set of polynomials $X = \{(f_{nj} \mid 0 \leq n \leq t; 1 \leq j \leq i_n)\}$. Clearly, $(X) \subset J$.

Conversely, the polynomials of degree 0 in J are precisely the elements of I_0 and hence are contained in (X) . Proceeding by induction assumes that (X) contains all polynomials of J of degree less than k and let $g \in J$ have degree k and leading coefficient $r \neq 0$. If $k \leq t$, then $r \in I_k$, and hence $r = s_1 r_{k1} + s_2 r_{k2} + \dots + s_{i_k} r_{ki_k}$ for some $s_j \in R$. Therefore, the polynomial

$$\sum_{j=1}^{i_k} s_j f_{kj} \in (X)$$

has leading coefficient r and degree k . Consequently,

$$g - \sum_j s_j f_{kj}$$

has degree at most $k - 1$. By the induction hypothesis

$$g - \sum_j s_j f_{kj} \in (X)$$

, whence $g \in (X)$. If $k \geq t$, then $r \in I_t$ and

$$r \in \sum_{j=1}^{i_t} s_j r_{tj} (s_j \in R)$$

. Furthermore,

$$\sum_{j=1}^{i_t} s_j x^{k-t} f_{tj} \in (X)$$

has leading coefficient r and degree k . Thus

$$g - \sum_j s_j x^{k-t} f_{tj}$$

has degree at most $k - 1$ and lies in (X) by the induction assumption. Consequently, $g \in (X)$ and the induction is complete. Therefore, $J = (X)$. The proof is again complete.

3 Applications

In this section, we will talk about other useful results and applications of the theorem we proved in Section 2 above.

Theorem 3.1. If D is a division ring, then the ring $Mat_n D$ of all $n \times n$ matrices over D is Noetherian.

Proof. Omitted.

Theorem 3.2. If R is a Noetherian integral domain that is not a field, then every nonzero nonunit in R can be factored into irreducibles.

Proof. Omitted.

Proposition 3.3. Let J be an ideal in a commutative ring R with identity. Then J is contained in every maximal ideal of R if and only if for every R -module A satisfying the ascending chain condition on submodules, $\bigcap_{n=1}^{\infty} J^n A = 0$

proof. (\implies) If $B = \bigcap_n J^n A$, then $JB = B$ by Krull Intersection theorem. Since B is finitely generated by Theorem 2.3.1, $B = 0$ by Nakayama's Lemma.

(\impliedby) We may assume $R \neq 0$. If M is any maximal ideal of R , then $M \neq R$ and $A = R/M$ is a nonzero R -module that has no proper submodules. Thus, A trivially satisfies the ascending chain condition; hence, $\bigcap_n J^n A = 0$ by hypothesis. Since JA is a submodule of A , either $JA = A$ or $JA = 0$. If $JA = A$, then $J^n A = A$ for all n . Consequently, $\bigcap_n J^n A = A \neq 0$, which is a contradiction. Hence, $JA = 0$. But $0 = JA = J(R/M)$ implies that $J \subset JR \subset M$. The proof is complete

Corollary 3.4. If R is a Noetherian local ring with maximal ideal M , $\bigcap_{n=1}^{\infty} M^n = 0$.

proof. If $J = M$ and $A = R$, then $J^n A = M^n$ then we apply Proposition 3.3.

Proposition 3.5. If R is a local ring, then every finitely generated projective R -module is free.

proof. Omitted.

Proposition 3.6. If R is a commutative Noetherian ring with identity, then so is $R[[x]]$.

Proof. omitted.

References

1. Thomas W. Hungerford, Graduate Texts in Mathematics Algebra, Springer
2. Keith Conrad, Notes on the Noetherian Rings.
3. Wikipedia note on the Noetherian Rings
4. Eisenbud, David (1995). Commutative Algebra with a View Toward Algebraic Geometry Graduate Texts in Mathematics Vol. 150. Springer-Verlag. doi:10.1007/978-1-4612-5350-1. ISBN 0-387-94268-8.
5. Kaplansky, I., "Projective Modules," Math. Ann., 68 (1958), pp. 372–377.